

ADVANTAGES OF USING E-BOOKS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LITERATURE

Akhmedov Rafael Sharifovich
senior lecturer, Gulistan State University
Khatamov Oybek Farhod og'li
student, Gulistan State University

Abstract. This article examines and comprehensively discusses the advantages of using electronic text in the process of teaching foreign literature to students of higher educational institutions at the present stage of development of the education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The analysis of advantages of e-books made it possible to overview perspective ways of using them in the process of teaching foreign literature.

For a literature teacher, working with text is not limited to reading the works of art or checking students' written works. Let's highlight two important elements that are present in the practice of any teacher of literature: 1) preparing your own materials for the lesson; 2) preparation of handouts for students. When preparing for the lesson, a teacher often needs to compile various texts for a synopsis: to build a methodological logic, to include quotation material in the synopsis, and finally, to directly prepare fragments of text for analysis. How are these notes created? Teachers, especially the older generation, have thick notebooks containing topics that are organized into blocks. The main content of these notebooks is handwritten texts, which contain many bibliographic references to the teacher's publications, sometimes accompanied by embedded clippings from other sources (for example, from methodological journals).

This information storage format has some obvious disadvantages:

1. Usually, it takes more than one year to create such textbooks on all teaching topics: a good teacher gradually expands, modifies, and supplements the material.
2. The notebook is gradually coming to an end, unnecessary material cannot be removed correctly (you can glue the pages, delete outdated ones, but the appearance and usability suffer from this), gradually this notebook becomes unusable.
3. These materials are very difficult to replicate. One handwritten summary is the main thing the teacher uses. It is possible to make a copy of this material (for example, on a photocopier), but usually its quality is poor. The loss of such a notebook leads to the loss of all information and practically destroys many years of work.
4. There is no possibility of fragmentary copying. This could be attributed to the previous point, but in this case I would like to emphasize something else: some of the information from the teacher's notes cannot be used by others. So, for example, a teacher cannot give a fragment of his notebook to a student or colleague for work [1].

Thus, teacher faces inconvenience in using such information medium that lacks functionality and flexibility. Today, using information technology, this component of pedagogical activity associated with the preparation of materials for a lesson can be optimized. At the same time, what is important, there is practically no need to master serious user skills: even a teacher who has been trained in the field of elementary computer literacy is able to more conveniently organize his activities.

Let's list the skills that are necessary for a teacher of literature to switch from paper to electronic media of "lesson" information.

1. Some experience of working with Internet resources (for example, to search for e-books in online libraries or philological materials on specialized sites).
2. Experience with the Microsoft Word text editor, which allows you to create a new unique material, collect material from various sources, and compile it for the task at hand [2].

Undoubtedly, transferring all the notes from paper to electronic versions is a huge job that can be done in more than one month. But if you think about it, it turns out to be easier than handwriting notes and other materials for the lesson. At the output, you can get not a single copy of the material, but text, in which you can make adjustments at any time and in any amount, delete outdated, add new,

change the type of text for a new task, split the text into fragments (for example, for distribution to students) and much more.

And another important point is connected to the fact that the concept of a portfolio is gradually entering the life of a teacher [3]. Certification, submission of competitive materials, filling in resources of your page on the educational platform – these are situations in which electronic versions of methodological and didactic materials will be very useful.

Let's consider another example. Teachers often have to prepare test papers for students, in particular those related to the analysis of fragments of a literary text. For example, the simplest type of such work is the recognition of a hero by a verbal portrait, speech characteristics, and behavioral features. To prepare the audience for such work, and even in terms of options, you need to spend a lot of time: rewrite the text by hand or type it on a typewriter. The ability to work with electronic texts greatly facilitates the task: in the network library we find the text, select the fragments necessary for work from it, copy them, then insert them into the electronic document and print the required number of copies. Preparation of such works takes a little time. As a result, you can have a whole set of verification and diagnostic work on all topics of the course. In the same way, you can prepare handouts for lessons – fragments of texts for analysis, poems, quotes from critical and literary books.

Let's see what the teacher gets when working with electronic materials.

1. "All yours is always with you." Portable storage devices (so-called "flash drives", and portable hard drives) are getting cheaper every year, and the teacher can have all his working materials at hand: texts of works, synopses, fragments of students' work, graphic images, etc.

2. "Abstract in 5 minutes." Fast compilation of any texts. Opening a new file in Microsoft Word, copying materials from different sources, pasting them into a new document - we get the necessary "here and now" material. From the available materials, you can easily make tests for students. For example, many teachers practice testing their knowledge of the text of a work through quick tests.

3. "Lack of abstracts". As any teacher knows, in a regular classroom, students of the auditory and visual types of perception coexist. It is easier for the former to perceive the material by ear, while the latter is more convenient if it is presented graphically (for example, on a blackboard). Today, the number of adolescents who are visuals is much more than students who can listen and hear. Work in the lesson often boils down to the fact that the student is required to dynamically switch perceptions and actions (now we listen, then discuss, then write down). Even senior students find it difficult not to lose the thread of the lesson and at the same time record its progress in writing, in the form of a synopsis, which we often invite them to conduct. Writing down words, they lose their general meaning, logic, emotional mood. Meanwhile, the existence of electronic versions of materials that at the end of the lesson all students can receive from the teacher (in electronic form or in printouts - it does not matter), could allow students to focus on the course of the lesson itself, on the teacher's words and statements of fellow students and work more productively.

Today, one can often hear the opinion that the paper book as an information medium is becoming obsolete, that after a while its existence will be determined not by its functional, but by its cultural and historical role. To avoid disputes in which personal preferences are expressed in one way or another, let us try to rationally compare the features of a paper and an electronic book.

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of E-Books and Paper Books

Feature	Paper Book	E-Book
Storage	Requires space, which depends on the volume	Does not take up space in physical meaning, in the computer's memory it takes up a very small space
Reading	Perception depends on the characteristics of editions (for example, font, lighting)	Binding to a computer, the difficulty of reading of large text arrays from the screen.

		Although recently there have appeared special devices ("book readers")
Replication	Impossible or with significant restrictions	Possible
Safety	It ages and deteriorates over time, requires careful handling	"Eternal" (at a certain level of user's competence)
Additional Functions	Only text + graphics, the quality of which due to the peculiarities of the publication	Hyperlinks to audio or video files can be inserted to a computer file of e-book, the text itself can be accompanied by any type of graphic information
Price	High, a significant part of it is due to the price of paper and due to the profit desired by publisher	Lower than paperback, sometimes even free (today many online bookstores sell e-books)
Interaction with a Reader	Notes in the book spoil it (often regarded as vandalism), compilation of the fragments is impossible, search is difficult	Ability to make notes on the fields, bookmark, search, highlight, edit, copy text; possibility quickly return to its original state
Tradition of Perception	Many centuries	Still unusual for a wide range of readers, but becomes more and more common for new generation

The comparison shows that there are some features that determine the superiority of an electronic book over a paper one, at least in the field of education. Today this is hindered not so much by technological capabilities as by the inertia of perception of readers who are accustomed to holding a book in their hands and turning the pages, rather than pressing buttons while looking at the screen. However, in some universities of Uzbekistan in literature lessons today, about 30% of students use telephones, tablets or laptops in which the texts of the studied works are written. And they are quite capable of performing the tasks that others do when working with a paper book: highlighting keywords, quotes, working with comments. Why are they sitting with "Robert Frost" on display? Because there were no books at home, there were no books left in the university library, and there was not enough time to go to the district library. Previously, such a student would simply declare that he did not have the book. Today he works with its electronic version. So it is hardly worth categorically asserting that the computer replaces books - in some cases it returns them.

From the above table, we can conclude that, compared to paper media, an e-book consists of some advantages. The answer to this question depends on the point of view of the problem. There is an important emotional component: favorite collected works in the closet since childhood, the tactile sensation of turning the pages of books, bookshelves in the apartment as a sign of an intelligent family. But here we must admit that what has been described rather refers not to literature, not to reading, but to a greater extent to book culture. Let's split the reading process into two. On the one hand, reading as a functional process, in which the comfort of reading, speed, the ability to enter into a dialogue with the text and make it "your own", the convenience of long-term storage, combined with the speed of access if necessary, are important. On the other hand, the book remains a cultural artifact, and the attitude towards it is somewhat similar to the attitude towards books in antiquity, when the content is inextricably linked with the design. It seems to us that periodicals, professional and entertainment literature (something that should always be at hand, or something that can be read

once and deleted) will completely disappear into the electronic format, and works of printing art will remain, for example, architectural or painting albums. good editions of classical literature. The "functional" book will become completely electronic, but as a cultural phenomenon, the "aesthetic" paper book will coexist with it. You can treat these phenomena in different ways, the most reasonable, in our opinion, is to accept and try to get used to it. Progress often leaves us no other choice.

References

1. Brusilovsky P., Chavan G., Farzan R. Social Adaptive Navigation Support for Open Corpus Electronic Textbooks. In: De Bra P.M.E., Nejd W. (Eds.), Adaptive Hypermedia and Adaptive Web-Based Systems // Lecture Notes in Computer Science. – 2004. Vol. 3137. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-540-27780-4_6
2. Lin Y.-C., Liu T.-C. & Kinshuk. Research on Teachers' Needs When Using E-Textbooks in Teaching // Smart Learning Environments. – 2015. Vol. 2(1). DOI: 10.1186/s40561-014-0008-1
3. Soan T., Herman N.D., Maknun J. E-Books in Teaching & Learning Process // Proceedings of the 5th UPI International Conference on Technical and Vocational Education and Training. – 2018. Vol. 299. – P. 281-287. DOI: 10.2991/ictvet-18.2019.64